

Experiential Concepts in Design Research : A (Not Too) Critical Review

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Position Paper

Theoretical Issues theme

Abstract

Interest in the affective qualities of the human-product relationship has inspired researchers to study all kinds of affective phenomena. As a consequence, the literature reports a wide variety of experiential concepts, either devised in and for the design domain, or borrowed from other research domains. Although the multitude of concepts is valuable for the enrichment and expansion of the domain, the loose relation between those seemingly different concepts also hinders a common ground for discussion. In this paper we aim to identify, define, and classify nine experiential concepts that can be found in design research literature. These nine concepts have been discussed in two conferences with a main focus on affective issues in design (research): ‘design and emotion’ and ‘designing pleasurable products and interfaces,’ and were collected by reviewing all papers that refer to an experiential concept in their title and/or abstracts. In order to structure the review, a framework of experience was employed that distinguishes three levels of product experience: aesthetic pleasure, attribution of meaning, and emotional response. Although related, these levels have their own and distinct lawful underlying processes. The review demonstrates an approach to distinguishing and comparing experiential concepts, and the resulting structure can contribute to a general understanding of approaches to experience in the domain of design research, and stimulate new research directions yet to be explored.

Keywords

Product experience, Affect, Aesthetics of interaction, Attachment, Attraction, Engagement, Enjoyment, Luxury Experience, Playfulness, Resonance, WOW experience.

Introduction

The interest in affect research is relatively new because, whereas philosophy has a rich tradition in this topic, psychology has traditionally shown more interest in behaviour and cognition than in experience. In the sixties, affect found its way (back) to the psychologists' research agenda, and some influential books have been published since. Arnold (1960) paved the path for modern emotion psychology, and in her footsteps some leading researchers, like Frijda (1986), Lazarus (1991), and Ortony, Clore and Collins. (1988), have built extensive frameworks that explain the basics of affect, how and why affect is elicited, and what phenomena are involved. At the same time, affect also started to attract attention in various other disciplines with a traditional focus on behaviour and cognition, such as marketing, consumer research, ergonomics, economics, and computer science. Marketing researchers use insights in affect to capture pleasurable (see Jordan, 1999) or desirable consumer experiences (see Schmitt, 1999). In the field of ergonomics, affect theory is used to explore processes involved in product usage, such as learning, problem solving, and motivation. Picard (1997), for example, discussed the role of affect in user-product communication. Helander and Tham (2003) demonstrated the importance of affect for ergonomics, Vink (2005) discussed the role of affect in comfort, and Tractinsky, Katz, and Ikar. (2000) indicated a relationship between affect and usability. Consumer researchers have shown an interest in affect because of the eminent influence of experience on consumer behaviour. Creusen (1998) showed that affective responses to product appearance influence purchase decisions, and Oliver (1993) discussed the relationship between affect and post-purchase product evaluation.

Although these are only few of many examples, they illustrate that the variety in objectives has stimulated disciplines to develop customised terminologies of experiential concepts. Design research takes a special place because design is an integrating discipline that requires aesthetic, marketing, ergonomic, and engineering skills. This multidisciplinary nature stimulated the variety of terminologies to enter the realm of design research. Besides adopting concepts of other disciplines, the design research community has also introduced some new concepts. The result is a research agenda dominated by a multitude of experiential concepts that, to some extent, differ in terms of described affective phenomena, theoretical backgrounds, research purposes, and design possibilities. Although the multitude of concepts is valuable for the enrichment and expansion of

the domain, the loose relation between those seemingly different concepts hinders a common ground for discussion. These considerations motivated us to make an attempt to identify, define, and classify experiential concepts that have been introduced in the design research literature. In this paper, which is a summary of a more extensive review that is in preparation, we report the resulting overview. Note that this overview is not aimed to be complete, but to provide a structure that facilitates comparisons between experiential concepts. In doing so, we hope to contribute to a general understanding of approaches to experience in the domain of design research, and to identify blank spots that can stimulate new research directions.

Approach

All experiential concepts discussed in this paper have been introduced in the conference proceedings of ‘design and emotion’ (McDonagh, Hekkert, van Erp and Gyi, 2004; Kurtgözü, 2004) or ‘designing pleasurable products and interfaces’ (Green and Jordan 2002; Hanington and Forlizzi, 2003; Wensveen, 2005). These conferences were selected because their main focus is on affective issues in design (research). All papers that refer to an experiential concept in their title and/or abstract have been reviewed. Given the limited space, the current overview does not include concepts that have been addressed extensively in other publications, such as pleasure (Jordan, 1999) and co-experience (e.g. Battarbee, 2004).

Experience framework

Product experience

The words affect and experience have been used interchangeably in the introduction because an experience is always affective. Affect signifies valence, i.e. pleasant or unpleasant, positive or negative (see Russell, 2003, and Ortony, Clore and Collins, 1988), and product experience is the affective response of a person interacting with a product. Note that with human-product interaction we do not only refer to instrumental interaction (e.g. using, operating, managing), but also to non-instrumental (e.g. playing with, caressing), and to non-physical interaction (e.g. remembering, anticipating usage). The experience is shaped by the characteristics of the user (e.g. personality, skills, and background) and those of the product (e.g. shape, texture, colour, and behaviour). All actions and processes that are involved, like physical actions, perceptual and cognitive processes (e.g. perceiving, exploring, using, remembering, comparing, and

understanding), will contribute to the experience (see also Dewey, 1980). In addition, the experience is always influenced by the context (e.g. physical, social, economical) in which the interaction takes place.

Product experience framework

In this paper we adopt the framework of Hekkert (2006) in which he distinguishes three components of product experience: aesthetic pleasure, attribution of meaning, and emotional response. Hekkert thus defines a product experience as “the entire set of effects that is elicited by the interaction between a user and a product, including the degree to which all our senses are gratified (aesthetic experience), the meanings we attach to the product (experience of meaning), and the feelings and emotions that are elicited (emotional experience)”. These three components or levels of the experience can be distinguished in having their own, albeit highly related, and lawful underlying processes.

At the aesthetic level, we consider a product’s capacity to delight one or more of our sensory modalities. A product can be beautiful to look at, make a pleasant sound, feel good to touch, or even smell nice. The degree to which a perceptual system manages to detect structure, order or coherence and assess a product’s novelty/ familiarity typically determine the affect that is generated (e.g., Gaver and Mandler, 1989; Hekkert, Snelders, and van Wieringen, 2003). As some authors argue, such effects can be explained by examining the evolutionary basis of our perceptual systems (e.g., Ramachandran and Hirstein, 1999; see Hekkert, 2006 for an overview). It is this level of sensory pleasure Norman (2004) is referring to in discussing the visceral level of emotional design and that Crilly, Moultrie and Clarkson (2004) treat as the cognitive response category ‘aesthetic impression’. We claim there are no emotions, nor cognitive processes at stake at this level.

At the level of meaning, cognition comes into play. Through cognitive processes like interpretation, memory retrieval, and associations we are able to recognize metaphors, assign personality or other expressive characteristics, and assess the personal or symbolic significance of products. This component of the experience corresponds with Crilly et al.’s (2004) cognitive

response categories 'semantic interpretation' and 'symbolic association'. It is clear that the cognitive processes involved are vulnerable to individual and cultural differences. Recently it has been shown that our body also plays a major role in understanding linguistic expressions (e.g., Gibbs, 2003; Lakoff and Johnson, 1980) and figurative expressions of products (Van Rompay, Hekkert, Saakes, and Russo, 2005).

At the emotional level, finally, we refer to those affective phenomena typically considered in emotion psychology and everyday language about emotions, love and disgust, fear and desire, pride and despair, to name a few. According to the currently most widely adopted theory of emotions, i.e. appraisal theory, an emotion is elicited by an evaluation (appraisal) of an event or situation as potentially beneficial or harmful (e.g., Arnold, 1960; Scherer, Schorr, and Johnstone, 2001; see also Desmet, 2002 for an overview). It is the interpretation of an event (or product), rather than the event itself, which causes the emotion. Contrary to popular belief, an emotion is thus the result of a, although often automatic and unconscious, cognitive process.

To further illustrate the distinction between the three components of the experience, let us look at some of our experiences with everyday products. When the user is pleased by the sensuous form of a vase, the silent but harmonic sound of a cellular phone, or the soft and fluffy texture of a seat, these experiences refer to aesthetic experiences. On the other hand, considering a coffee maker as masculine and very much 'for you', a mobile phone sexy, but perfectly clear and understandable, and a new car referring to the sixties, are all examples belonging to the experience of a product's meaning. When the user is enjoying the usage of an mp3 player, inspired by the novel design solution for a chair, or disgusted by the ideological associations of a particular type of outfit, we can identify these experiences as emotional experiences. Although these three components of an experience can thus be clearly conceptually separated, they are very much intertwined and impossible to distinguish in our everyday experience. We experience the unity of sensuous delight, meaningful interpretation, and emotional involvement, and only in this unity we speak of an experience. Nevertheless the distinction is valuable because it enables us to study and clarify the concepts found.

Experiential concepts in the design literature

Below, those concepts that were not easily identified as belonging to one of the three levels of product experience are discussed. The main focus of these concepts is visualised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Experiential concepts in relation to the experience framework

Aesthetics of interaction

With the concept of 'aesthetics of interaction' Overbeeke and Wensveen (2003) refer to the beauty of use, that is, the beauty one experiences when physically interacting with a product. This concept belongs to the aesthetic level of experience with a specific focus on the tactile and kinaesthetic, rather than on the visual aesthetics. Some approaches have been discussed to design for aesthetic interactions. As a general design goal, Overbeeke and Wensveen (2003) focus on the perceptual-motor skills of users in order to aim for richness in sensorial experiences and action possibilities. In his discussion of tangible interactions Zimmerman, Hurst and Peeters (2005) refers to Durrell Bishop's marble telephone answering machine, which creates enriched action possibilities by using marbles to represent digital messages.

Attachment

Most authors who discuss attachment will agree that this concept belongs to the meaning level of experience: we are attached to those products that have some profound and sustained meaning to us. Savaş (2004) for example, identifies feelings of confidence, independence, relaxation, achievement, security, friendship, and control. Note that also emotions can be involved in product attachment. However, although one can for example be afraid of losing, or proud of owning a product that one is attached to, we do not consider these emotions to be a necessary condition for, but a consequence of the sustained meaning. We should also acknowledge the behavioural consequences of attachment. Mugge, Schifferstein and Schoormans (2004, pp 1) propose that “when a person is attached to an object, (s)he is more likely to handle the product with care, to repair it when it breaks down, and to postpone its replacement as long as possible.” This behavioural tendency, i.e. keeping the product, is the consequence of attachment that signifies the extraordinary relationship between a user and a product.

Attraction

Hilton (2004) explains attraction as an experience that is influenced by senses but shaped by feelings. This explanation illustrates that the concept of attraction actually refers to two separate experiential phenomena. First, attraction is influenced by senses, which illustrates that one can ‘find something attractive.’ In that case, the attraction clearly refers to an aesthetic experience. Second, attraction is shaped by feelings, which illustrates that someone can also be ‘attracted by’ a product. In that case attraction refers to an emotional experience. For that reason, we conclude that the concept of attraction can belong both to the aesthetic and the emotional level of experience.

Engagement

The concept of engagement was introduced to the design domain by researchers involved with narrative interaction design (e.g. Burke, 2004; Polaine, 2004). These authors explore the possibilities to engage users in emotional arcs of an interface in the same way a narrative can also pass emotions from a story to the reader. In that way, engagement refers to an intense interest emotional episode. The consequence of engagement is that the user detaches from reality and engrosses into the world presented by the product interface. Because of the strong focus on

emotions, we consider this concept to belong to the emotional level of experience. Note that engagement also affects the behavioural qualities of the interaction. Engaged users will invest energy in exploring and experiencing the product. Action can also be seen as a condition of engagement. Burke (2004) suggests that active participation of the user is a way to engage users in the narrative interaction, and that engagement is enhanced when the user creates or manipulates the story told by the interface.

Enjoyment

Although the concept of enjoyment has been discussed extensively in design literature (see e.g. Blythe, Overbeeke, Monk and Wright, 2004) our review included only one study that refers to enjoyment. In that study, Khong and Song (2003) discuss enjoyment in the domain of information technology (IT). In their view enjoyment is a dimension of interaction that can be defined as the extent to which the activity of usage is perceived to be enjoyable in its own right, apart from any performance consequences that may be anticipated. Given the fact that this definition does not focus on the concept itself, we decided to adopt the common view on enjoyment that characterises this concept as an emotion (see e.g. Lazarus, 1991), and therefore consider this concept to belong to the emotional level of experience.

Luxury experience

Most of the papers that discuss the concept of luxury experience refer to experiences of uniqueness and a rich lifestyle. Reinmoeller (2002, p. 125), for example, defines luxury as “...means of enjoyment of rich, comfortable lifestyle and the indulgence of pleasure.” Luxury experience is therefore considered to be a particular experience of meaning. Like in other cases, the experienced meaning may activate other levels of experience. Uotila, Falin and Aula (2005) refer to emotional experiences, such as instrumental pleasure referring to satisfaction, and aesthetic enjoyment. However, we believe these experiences to be consequences rather than conditions for the luxury experience. Both product characteristics and user characteristics that influence luxury experiences have been studied. Uotila et. al (2005), for example, identify product, user, and context as influential actors of the luxury experience. According to Reinmoeller (2002), luxury products are created by the use of material, processes, packaging, distribution and promotion that exceeds the level of standard products to allow for pleasure.

Playfulness

The reviewed literature provided us with only one definition of playfulness. Noyes and Littledale (2002) define playfulness as an individual's tendency to interact spontaneously, inventively, and imaginatively with microcomputers. This definition considers playfulness to be a quality of the interaction with a strong influence on behavioural aspects of interaction, such as the tendency to explore. Besides, playfulness, we believe, may induce experiences in different levels. In particular, playful interaction has the potential to evoke positive emotional experiences such as 'enjoyment'.

Resonance

In terms of experience, resonance is a metaphor that describes a particular quality of interaction. The core of the concept is an experienced perfect match between user and product (Hummels, 2005). Unlike other concepts, it is difficult to relate this concept to only one level of experience. According to Hummels (2006), all three levels of experience constitute integral parts of resonance, since the experience of match may take place at any one of these levels. Resonance may evoke further experiences in different levels of experience as well. Given this two-way relationship between the various levels of experience and resonance, we propose that this concept belongs to all three levels of experience. In addition, this concept involves other aspects of interaction, such as "...unique accompanying behaviour, heightened awareness and cognitive processing."(Hummels, 2005, p. 17).

WOW

Authors who refer to wow-experiences, focus on emotional conditions that are associated with the exclamation of 'wow.' Desmet, Porcelijn and van Dijk (2005) define wow as a composite of pleasant surprise, fascination and desire. Hazlett and Benedek (2005) refer to wow experience as a synonym of intense positive emotional responses to software products. Following these authors, we consider wow to be an intense and positive emotional experience. Some authors discuss the conditions for experiencing wow, which can include an aesthetic experience and an experience of meaning. Steen (2005), for example, identified feelings of nostalgia, fantasy, and sensorial experience, and Hazlett and Benedek (2005) identify product novelty and aesthetic appreciation as conditions for wow-experiences.

Discussion

This review illustrated that the discussion on user experience in the design research community draws on an extensive set of affective or experiential concepts. This variety in concepts is of value for a profound exploration of the complex and rich experiences people have while interacting with products. On the other hand, the drawback of entertaining a large variety of sometimes loosely defined concepts is the danger of fuzziness and ambiguity, which in the worst case can frustrate rather than facilitate fruitful discussion. With this review we hope to launch an attempt to provide some conceptual clarity by using an experience framework to compare and contrast experiential concepts. Note that because several of the concepts were only loosely defined, occasionally interpretation from our side was required. In addition, several of the reported definitions do not accord with those that can be found outside our review domain. We believe that social sciences, and in particular psychology, offer clear bases for experiential concepts that can structure some of the discussion in the design domain.

This framework should be considered as part of an ongoing dialogue in which one topic of discussion is the relevance of each of the various concepts for the enrichment of the research domain. We saw that some concepts can be distinguished in terms of the level of experience they were referring to (e.g. wow, which is emotional, and aesthetic interactions, which is aesthetic), and others do not differ in terms of the level of experience but in terms of the particular experience they refer to (e.g. wow and enjoyment, which are both emotional). Moreover, some of the concepts are not only distinguished in terms of experience, but also in terms of other aspects of the interaction. A clear example is attachment, which has a strong behavioral component besides the experience of meaning that gives rise to it. Some of the concepts seem to describe experiences that are more ecologically valid than others. With this validity we refer to those concepts that we can easily imagine to experience or see experienced in everyday life. These concepts, such as enjoyment and attachment, are relatively easy to operationalize for empirical investigations. Those that are more ‘creative,’ like resonance, appear to have a different value for the research arena. They can be stimulating or inspirational in a context that is more explorative or generative than empirical. These are not so much real experiences but metaphors of experience that, because they capture experiential qualities of the user-product relationship, can give direction to creativity with an experiential intent in research through design applications.

The basic framework can be deepened with the inclusion of sub branches within the three main levels of experience. This will facilitate the identification of blank spots that denote research opportunities. A second research area of interest is the mutual exclusiveness between the various concepts. It will further clarify the theoretical basis to identify the experiences that are evoked in relation to each other.

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